

ANXIETY DRIVEN BY MODULAR LEARNING: ITS IMPACT TO THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AS PERCEIVED BY THE THIRD YEAR GENERAL SCIENCE STUDENTS OF THE COLLEGE OF EDUCATION IN MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY-SULU: BASIS AS A WAY OF TRAVERSING THE CHALLENGE OF NEW NORMAL

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine if anxiety driven by modular learning has an impact on the academic performance as perceived by the third year general science students in Mindanao State University-Sulu. It explored further to determine the levels of anxiety driven by modular learning as perceived by the students, it also determined how can anxiety driven by modular learning affects the academic performance of the students and the interventions that may hinder anxiety driven by modular learning as perceived by the students. The study used descriptive research design where the researchers utilized a checklist questionnaire to acquire the data needed. The setting of the study was conducted at Mindanao State University-Sulu. Thirty-eight (38) students were the respondents of the study which are the third year general science students of the College of Education. Purposive sampling was used in selection of respondents and weighted mean was used as the statistical tool of the study. The questionnaire checklist was divided into three parts and each contains ten (10) statements and was administered of the first semester of A.Y 2020-2021.

Keywords: *anxiety, modular learning, academic performance, interventions, new normal*

INTRODUCTION

Anxiety is one of the biggest enemies of every individual be it in school, at home or even just vibing alone. Anxiety can be driven by so many factors including the people that surrounds you, the community you lived in, and the like. If anxiety has not been diagnosed as early as possible, it can lead to some serious problems like depression. The most prone to anxiety or the most affected by anxiety are those younger people who are fighting and striving for their future.

As defined by Ajmal and Ahmad (2019), anxiety is a basic human emotion that consists of fear and uncertainty and usually it occurs when individual believes that the event is a threat to self or self-esteem. Anxiety can also be state or trait depending on its duration. Anxiety blocks the normal thought processes. It favors a passive approach to material rather than interaction with it. Anxiety is the human emotion that everyone experiences. Students experience problems during their studies, and feel anxious when taking exams or making significant life decisions. There is evidence in the literature that there is a negative correlation between anxiety and student achievement, and there is a negative correlation between anxiety and the realization of important cognitive and emotional outcomes in distance learning education (Jegede, Alaiyemola, & Okebukola, 1990).

By this time, maybe the pandemic is gone but we can't deny that its trace still remains thus education must not stop. In order to continue the learning of the youths, the government has come up with a solution to render the needs of the students because we all believe that education is the key to success so it must not be disrupted. The idea of continuing education has been on the line since it is one of the priorities of the government; the learnings of the students.

Nevertheless, as stated by DepEd (2020), President Rodrigo Duterte mandated the Department of Education (DepEd) to delay, if not, cancel face-to-face teaching for as long as the vaccine for the coronavirus disease is not yet made available to the public. However, opting not to delay education, DepEd introduced alternative learning delivery modalities that utilize modern technology.

The solution that the government has made to continue educating the youth is the so-called distance learning. Wherein students receive instruction through online classes, video recordings, video conferencing, or any other audio/visual technology medium (Loveless, 2021). The teaching instruction can also be done through modular classes which our province is now utilizing to render the needs of the students in terms of learning.

According to Mark Llego (2021), modular distance learning involves individualized instruction that allows learners to use self-learning modules (SLMs) in print or digital format/electronic copy, whichever is applicable in the context of the learner, and other learning resources. With regards to this, the emphasis and goal of our educator is to continue the educational process of all student amidst the pandemic. In order to retain and continue their learning process and their academic performances.

However, the sudden change in students' learning has brought change to some students' mental health. And according to International Board of Credentialing and Continuing Education Standards (2019), students who have undiagnosed anxiety can negatively impact their ability to learn and enjoy their time in school. When students have anxiety that goes unnoticed their mental health is at risk, which can lead to social and behavioral problems, poor performance and learning, neglected hygiene, poor self-care practices and low self-esteem.

Furthermore, the main purpose of this study is to investigate if anxiety driven by modular learning has an impact on the academic performance of the Third Year College General Science Students Mindanao State University-Sulu.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to determine if anxiety driven by modular learning has an impact on the academic performance of the Third Year General Science Students in Mindanao State University-Sulu. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following:

1. What is the level of impact of anxiety driven by modular learning on the academic performance as perceived by the Third Year General Science Students of in Mindanao State University-Sulu?
2. How can anxiety have driven by modular learning affects the academic performance as perceived by the Third Year General Science Students in Mindanao State University-Sulu?
3. What are the interventions that may hinder the anxiety driven by modular learning on the academic performance as perceived by the Third Year General Science Students in Mindanao State University-Sulu?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The setting of the study was conducted at Mindanao State University-Sulu. The Mindanao State University-Sulu is the only university in Jolo, Sulu located at Capitol Site near the Provincial Capitol. The said university is composed of seven (7) colleges excluding the Mindanao State University-Sulu Laboratory High School. Particularly, this study is conducted at College of Education in between the College of Business Administration and College of Public Affairs.

Sampling Method

In this study, the researchers used Purposive Sampling or Judgement sampling to select the participant of the study. According to Crossman (2020), Purposive Sampling is a non-probability sample that is selected based on characteristics of a population and the

objective of the study.

Moreover, the respondents of this study are the Third Year General Science Students of the College of Education in Mindanao State University-Sulu which is comprised of thirty-eight (38) students – thirty regular students and 8 irregular students under Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in General Science.

Research Instrument

The researchers used Questionnaire checklist to obtain the needed information for this study and to help them answer the objectives of the study in finding out if anxiety driven by modular learning has an impact on the academic performance as perceived by the Third Year General Science Students in Mindanao State University-Sulu. Specifically, each questionnaire is divided into three parts. The first part of the questionnaire is the first statement of the problem which is the impact of anxiety on the academic performance as perceived by the students, the second part contains the second statement of the problem which is how can anxiety driven by modular learning affect the academic performance as perceived by the students and the last part of the questionnaire is the third statement of the problem which is interventions that may hinder anxiety driven by modular learning as perceived by the students.

Statistical Treatment of Data

For the analysis of data, the researchers used Weighted Mean as a statistical tool in dealing with the impact of anxiety driven by modular learning to the academic performance as perceived by the students, how can anxiety driven by modular learning affect the academic performance as perceived by the students and the interventions that may hinder anxiety driven by modular learning and its impact on the academic performance as perceived by the Third Year General Science Students in Mindanao State University-Sulu.

Scope and Delimitation

This study focuses on the anxiety driven by modular learning and its impact to the academic performance as perceived by the students in Mindanao State University-Sulu. The participant of this study is delimited to the Third Year General Science Students of the College of Education. Furthermore, the study is to be conducted only in College of Education in Mindanao State University-Sulu. The study is confined in the second semester of the academic year 2020-2021.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4.1 Level of impact of anxiety driven by modular learning on the academic performance as perceived by the students.

STATEMENTS	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. Anxiety driven by modular learning makes me uncomfortable during my study time.	2.78	Moderately High Impact
2. I cannot interact with other people.	2.78	Moderately High Impact
3. Anxiety lessens my motivation to do my school works.	2.86	Moderately High Impact
4. It helps me coping with stress due to my school works.	2.55	Moderately High Impact
5. Anxiety helps me to be independent.	2.73	Moderately High Impact
6. It makes me improved my academic performance.	2.31	Low Impact
7. Anxiety disturbed my concentration in answering the learning materials.	3.36	High Impact
8. It enhanced my capacity during the modular learning.	2.36	Low Impact
9. Anxiety lessens my will to learn.	2.71	Moderately High Impact
10. Anxiety makes me introverted and lose self-improvement.	2.89	Moderately High Impact
Overall Mean	2.733	Moderately High Impact

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (1) – VLI; 1.50-2.49 (2) – LI; 2.50-3.49 (3) – MHI; 3.50-4.00 (4) - HI

Table 4.1 shows the respondents' perspective about the level of impact of anxiety driven by modular learning and its impact on their academic performance during this pandemic. The majority of the students responded moderately high impact which has an overall mean of 2.733. This implies that most of the students' anxiety moderately impacted the academic performance which is brought by modular learning during this time of pandemic.

On the other hand, the respondents' prospect towards the statement numbers six (6) and eight (8) is low impact with a weighted mean of 3.31 and 3.36 which indicates that the improvement on their academic performance has low impact due to anxiety and that the enhancement of their capabilities in relation to their academic performance has also low impact.

Additionally, according to Star (2020) these symptoms of anxiety are a common

problem from people who have been diagnosed with any type of anxiety disorder including panic disorder. However, have you ever considered some of the possible positive effects that may come with having anxiety? Good stress, something now referred to now as eustress keeps us motivated and excited about life. It appears that some degree of anxiety may have similar “silver linings.” However, students answered high impact on number seven (7) which gained a weighted mean of 3.36 which implies that anxiety disturbed their concentration in answering their learning materials.

In addition to that, as cited by Better Health Channel (2017) anxiety disorders can affect a person’s ability to work, study and participate in other activities and anxiety symptoms are associated with impairment of memory and cognitive functions which might interfere with general wellbeing, social life, academic performance, learning ability, and development of social relationships (Afolayan, Donald, Onasoga, Babafemi, & Juan, 2013; Mazzone et al., 2007; McDonald, 2001; Neil & Donald, 2010).

Furthermore, the findings showed that the level of impact of anxiety driven by modular learning to the academic performance of the students is moderately high impact with a weighted mean of 2.73 which only implies that as stated by Dash (2021) levels of anxiety can be influenced by personality, coping strategies, life experiences, and gender.

Finally, moderately high of anxiety have more frequent symptoms than those with mild anxiety, but still have better daily functioning than someone with severe anxiety or panic disorder. For example, people with moderate anxiety may report experiencing symptoms such as feeling on edge, being unable to control their worrying or being unable to relax several days or the majority of days in a week, but not every day (Dash, 2021).

Table 4.2 Anxiety driven by modular learning affect the academic performance as perceived by the Third Year General Science students of the COED.

STATEMENTS	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. Anxiety helps me to develop my critical thinking.	2.36	Disagree
2. Anxiety leads me to stress and frustration due to modular learning.	3.26	Strongly Agree
3. Anxiety drives me to imagine unimportant and unnecessary things that are not related to my studies.	3.05	Agree
4. It makes me a great problem-solver.	2.42	Disagree
5. It motivates me to self-explanatory.	2.60	Agree
6. It helps me improve my writing and reading comprehension.	2.26	Disagree
7. Anxiety leads me to uncomfortable physical sensation which affects my studies.	3.02	Agree

8. I cannot focus due to intense fear and worry.	3.36	Strongly Agree
9. Anxiety gives me a low self-esteem.	3.31	Strongly Agree
10. It is difficult for me to understand my modules due to anxiety.	3.5	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	2.914	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (1) – VLI; 1.50-2.49 (2) – LI; 2.50-3.49 (3) – MHI; 3.50-4.00 (4) – HI

Table 4.2 shows that the perspective of the respondents towards how anxiety driven by modular learning affects the academic performance of the students. Majority of the students answered agree which has an overall mean of 2.914. This implies that the respondents agreed that anxiety driven by modular learning affects the academic performance of the students on some cases like they often times overthink but they can also develop their skills in self-explanatory wherein they know how to express their self when they are heard or needs a therapy called cognitive therapy as stated by Better Health Channel (2017).

Meanwhile, students responded disagree with a weighted mean of 2.36, 2.42 and 2.26 on the numbers one (1), four (4) and six (6) which refers to the following statement namely: anxiety helps them to develop their critical thinking, anxiety makes them a great problem-solver and anxiety helps them in improving their writing and reading skills. Students most likely feel that anxiety did not help them to become the best version of their selves. Because as cited by Katharina Star (2020), anxiety is a feeling that is often characterized by intense fear, worry, and apprehension. Many individuals with anxiety describe it as a feeling of nervousness and dread that can be distracting at best and all-consuming at worst.

Additionally, students strongly agree on the numbers two (2), eight (8), nine (9) and ten (10) with a weighted mean of 3.26, 3.36, 3.31, and 3.50 where on the respondents' perspective, anxiety leads them to stress and frustration due to modular learning, they cannot focus due to intense fear and worry, anxiety gives them low self-esteem and it is difficult for them to understand their modules due to anxiety. The American Psychological Association (APA) defines anxiety as "an emotion characterized by feelings of tension, worried thoughts and physical changes like increased blood pressure." And anxiety is a feeling that is often characterized by intense fear, worry, and apprehension. Many individuals with anxiety describe it as a feeling of nervousness and dread that can be distracting at best and all-consuming at worst (Star, 2020).

The respondents perceived that anxiety driven by modular learning can affect the academic performance of the students, which implies they agree that it affects their psychological well-being. An individual exhibiting a combination of low mood, showing no interest or pleasure, guilt, low self-esteem, disturbed appetite, disturbed sleep, and disturbed concentration is termed depressed (Marcus et al., 2012). However, when a person regularly feels disproportionate levels of anxiety, it might become a medical disorder (Felman, 2020).

Table 4.3 Interventions that may hinder anxiety driven by modular learning on the academic performance as perceived by the students.

STATEMENTS	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. I encourage myself to be mindful at all times.	3.10	Agree
2. I allow myself to be exposed in some activities in school.	3.02	Agree
3. Self-talk really help me to motivate myself.	3.36	Strongly Agree
4. I do not like to mingle with other people.	2.68	Agree
5. I will allow myself to get relaxed from stress.	3.26	Strongly Agree
6. Stimulating assertiveness will help me to develop my self-esteem.	3.07	Agree
7. I seldom eat green leafy vegetables because I like processed food.	2.86	Agree
8. I seldom seek an advice from our guidance councilor at school.	2.86	Agree
9. I talk to my parents regarding my personal problems and school works to help me in dealing with my stress and anxiety.	2.94	Agree
10. Exercising helps me reduce stress and somehow remove the negativities in me and clear my mind.	3.39	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.057	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (1) – VLI; 1.50-2.49 (2) – LI; 2.50-3.49 (3) – MHI; 3.50-4.00 (4) – HI

Table 4.3 presents the interventions that may hinder anxiety driven by modular learning as perceived by the students gained an over-all mean of 3.057 which indicates that they agreed by the interventions that may hinder anxiety driven by modular learning. As stated by Better Health Channel (2017), recovery is possible with appropriate treatment such as exposure therapy, attention training, and a range of anxiety management techniques that can help you manage your symptoms. You can learn the following strategies yourself (using books or taking courses, for example) or you can consult with a trained professional.

On the other hand, the students answered strongly agree on the following numbers of indication: three (3) with a weighted mean of 3.36, five (5) with a weighted mean of 3.26, and ten (10) with a weighted mean of 3.39 by which they strongly agreed on self-talk really help them to motivate their selves, they will allow their selves to get relax from stress and exercising helps them in reducing stress and somehow remove the negativities in them and it can clear their mind. These are some effective interventions that the respondents perceived which is similar to the studies of Better Health Channel (2017) where they cited that cognitive therapy strategies which includes rational ‘self-talk’, reality testing, attention training, cognitive challenging and cognitive restructuring. This includes monitoring your self-talk, challenging unhelpful fears and beliefs, and testing out the reality of negative thoughts.

Additionally, Simple activities can help soothe the mental and physical signs of anxiety

and physical exertion can improve self-image and release chemicals in the brain that trigger positive feelings (Better Health Channel, 2017).

Anxiety itself is not a medical condition but a natural emotion that is vital for survival when an individual finds themselves facing danger. Treatment involves a combination of different types of therapy, medication, and counseling, alongside self-help measures. An active lifestyle with a balanced diet can help keep anxious emotions within healthy limits (Better Health Channel, 2017).

Conclusions

The results revealed that anxiety driven by modular learning indeed has an impact to the academic performance as perceived by the students. The levels of anxiety driven by modular learning shows that it is moderately high which impacted the academic performance. And it also affects the academic performance of the students because students tend to imagine things which are irrelevant to their studies which became the reason why they are distracted and uncomfortable, hence the students tend to become passive when it comes to answering their learning materials through modular study. However, there are some interventions that can be done to avoid and to treat anxiety, it can be done through being assertive, mindful, allowing oneself to be exposed in some activities, exercising, self-talk, and having someone to talk with.

Hence, anxiety driven by modular learning indeed has an impact on the academic performance as perceived by the Third Year General Science Students in Mindanao State University-Sulu.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are forwarded:

1. Students should know how to manage their time in studying and in their personal lives to ensure that they are not distracted and that they can accomplish their task both in school and in their daily life.
2. Parents should have more time in monitoring the health of their children especially their mental health and they need to establish good communication in order to help their children in handling their personal dilemma.
3. Teachers should assess the activities to be given to the students if they can do it without having to stress their selves in answering their learning materials. And they also need to be understanding and patient when it comes to students who's having a mental breakdown. Lastly, teachers should also make their instructional material based on the capabilities of their students

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers hereby declare that an informed consent was obtained from the respondents of the study. In addition, the researchers assure that the information gathered from respondents are kept confidential. Plagiarism was strictly observed throughout the research process, and that there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research purposes.

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